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Editorial

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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

JIS Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences, Volume 1, Issue 1, November. (2017)

Editorial

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to announce the publication of its first issue in November 2017 bringing together an assessment of the articles from the interdisciplinary sciences. This issue covers subjects from the disciplines of education, engineering, humanities, and science. It is our pleasure to disseminate the deep well researched knowledge to the readership.

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an academic platform for author(s) and readers where researched knowledge and intelligence can be shared through that is assimilated from various interdisciplinary field of study. It is the journal mission to join and collaborate with authors to strengthen the hidden and scattered knowledge to disseminate widely through as JIS act as the proficient outlet for academic, scientific endeavor that supports and help the author(s) through the scientific peer review from the expert reviewers.

The beginning is yet a step forward for the JIS to embark on the life-wide and life-long academic journey. Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) commitment towards consistency in publication is another walk towards the academic journey. It has been a pleasure to share and learn from authors and reviewers from interdisciplinary sciences, which is also the mission of the JIS.

The next issue will be published in May 2018. We invite the authors, scientists, scholars, researchers, students, managers, leaders from interdisciplinary sciences to submit their papers.

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is thankful to all the editorial team, support team and the expert/advisors for their contributions. Most of all, JIS appreciate and is thankful to all the reviewers for their valuable input and scientific and academic rigor in commenting and suggesting the authors work and for their time spared to review the papers.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

JIS Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences, Volume 1, Issue 1, November. (2017)

Editorial

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Notes to Readers

Dear Readers,

It has been a remarkable journey with the publication of the November issue 2017. This issue brings articles from various disciplines to widely spread knowledge of the intelligent minds through the JIS online platform. It is therefore, the aims and focus of the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) to enhance the interdisciplinary academic areas.

The November issue thus, puts together the articles from various authors from across the continent with the perspectives on interdisciplinary studies. I strongly believe that the JIS forthcoming volume and issue in 2018 will succeed in consistent publication of the articles in future.

I therefore, on this note invite scholars from interdisciplinary studies to submit their papers of conceptual, essay, empirical from which we can work together to walk along the academic journey. On this note, I would like to thank the editorial team, advisors, experts and the reviewers who have played vital role in making the success of the volume 1, Issue 1 in November 2017.

I wish the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) in its first publication and enhancing the beautiful minds and intellectual journey.

With best of regards,
Professor Shireen Motala
Senior Director: UJ Postgraduate School
University of Johannesburg

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